

Estimation of Amino Acids in Seed Proteins

G. S. GROVER and J. TIRUMALA RAO*

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar (M. P.)

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The seeds of *Bupleurum falcatum*, *Holoptelea integrifolia*, *Oroxylum indicum* and *Ventilago calyculata* have been found to contain 2.1, 11.5, 7.9 and 3.5% protein respectively. The amino acids in the seed proteins have been estimated quantitatively using Moore and Stein spectrophotometric method. It has been found that *H. integrifolia* protein is rich in methionine; *O. indicum* is abundant with leucine and *V. calyculata* protein contains a high concentration of glycine.

AMINO acids produce distinct colours with ninhydrin which are stable, fading only 1-2% in 24 hrs. It has been shown^{1,2} that the maximum colour density procedure for the estimation of amino acids yields results which agree with other more involved methods. Moreover, the procedure is convenient, less tedious and rapid. According to Hyman Rosen³ the colour produced by ninhydrin and amino acids are except in few cases, almost the same at equal dilutions. Hence, a graph prepared from the optical densities of glycine-ninhydrin reaction at different concentrations of glycine can be used as standard reference for estimation of amino acids in the test samples. Present paper deals with the estimation of different amino acids in the seed proteins of *Bupleurum falcatum* (*N. O. Umbelliferae*), commonly known as 'Sickle Haris Ear' in English and 'Kalizewar' in Punjabi⁴; *Holoptelea integrifolia* (*N. O. Ulmaceae*), commonly known as 'Indian Elm' in English and 'Kanju', 'Papar', 'Chilbil' or 'Dhamina' in Hindi⁵; *Oroxylum indicum* (*N. O. Bignoniaceae*), commonly known as 'Indian Trumpet flower' in English and 'Arlu', 'Uliu' or 'Saona' in Hindi⁶ and *Ventilago calyculata* (*N. O. Rhamnaceae*), commonly known as 'Red creeper' in English and 'Raidhani', 'Keoti' or 'Kanyal' in Hindi⁷.

Experimental

Isolation of protein: The seed powders (100 g) were defatted, extracted with sodium chloride solution and protein were precipitated by adding hydrochloric acid to the saline extracts. The seeds of *B. falcatum*, *H. integrifolia*, *O. indicum* and *V. calyculata* were found to contain 2.1, 11.0, 7.9 and 3.5% crude protein respectively.

Identification of amino acids: Amino acids liberated from the protein by refluxing it (600 mg) with 100 ml of 6N HCl, were decolourised and dissolved in 10% isopropyl alcohol after removal of excess HCl by evaporation. This solution was used for chromatographic studies. The characterisation of amino acids was carried out by ascending, descending and two-dimensional paper chromatography on Whatman No. 1 paper strips. Paper strips in ascending and descending paper chromatography were developed with the upper layer

obtained on shaking a mixture of *n*-butanol, glacial acetic acid and water (4 : 1 : 5). Two dimensional chromatograms were developed with the above solvent in one direction and phenol saturated with water in the second direction. After development, the strips were dried and sprayed with modified ninhydrin reagent⁸ prepared by mixing solution I (0.1 g ninhydrin dissolved in 50 ml of absolute alcohol to which were added 10 ml glacial acetic acid and 2 ml of 2 : 4 : 6-collidine) and solution II (0.5 g copper nitrate dissolved in 50 ml of absolute alcohol) in a ratio of 50 : 3. It has been found that (i) the protein of *B. falcatum* contains arginine, valine, tryptophan, β -phenyl alanine, glycine, alanine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid and leucine, (ii) the protein of *H. integrifolia* contains alanine, arginine, aspartic acid, cystine, glutamic acid, glycine, lysine, histidine, proline, tyrosine and methionine, (iii) the protein of *O. indicum* contains cystine, arginine, leucine, isoleucine, histidine, aspartic acid, lysine, glycine, threonine, proline, hydroxy proline, tyrosine and β -phenyl alanine and (iv) the protein of *V. calyculata* contains cystine, arginine, leucine, valine, tryptophan, histidine, β -phenyl alanine, glycine, alanine, tyrosine, lysine, aspartic acid and proline.

Estimation of amino acids: For the estimation of amino acids a modified method of Moore and Stein⁹⁻¹² was used. Solutions of glycine of different concentrations (0.2, 0.175, 0.15, 0.1 and 0.05%) were prepared in absolute alcohol. Equal amounts of different dilutions of the glycine solutions were spotted on Whatman No. 1 filter paper strips and developed by descending paper chromatography. The chromatograms were dried and sprayed with ninhydrin. The coloured spots were cut out and eluted with 10 ml of 95% ethanol. The optical densities of the eluates were measured on Beckmann spectrophotometer at 570 m μ (Table 1) and a graph was drawn plotting concentration against optical density.

The developed amino acid spots of the test solutions of the seed proteins were also eluted separately with 10 ml of 95% ethanol and the optical densities corresponding to each amino acid were measured. The optical densities of all the amino acids were measured at 570 m μ except proline and

hydroxy proline which were read at 440 m μ . With the help of standard reference prepared above, the concentration of each amino acid of the test sample was calculated by interplotting their optical densities and their percentages calculated (Table 2).

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	%concentration of glycine	Optical density
1.	0.2	1.59
2.	0.175	1.4
3.	0.15	1.2
4.	0.1	0.75
5.	0.05	0.39

TABLE 2

Sl. Amino acid No.	%composition in the seed protein			
	<i>B. falcatum</i>	<i>H. integrifolia</i>	<i>O. indicum</i>	<i>V. calyculata</i>
1. Alanine	17.73	0.66	—	9.54
2. Arginine	5.17	6.12	9.27	6.08
3. Aspartic acid	19.08	8.28	5.56	6.90
4. Cystine	—	4.97	2.31	1.62
5. Glutamic acid	8.54	7.12	—	—
6. Glycine	8.61	1.45	7.41	30.94
7. Histidine	—	6.62	6.16	6.81
8. Hydroxyproline	—	—	8.34	—
9. Isoleucine	—	—	6.95	—
10. Leucine	8.55	—	30.60	4.78
11. Lysine	—	13.38	8.19	15.60
12. Methionine	—	33.02	—	—
13. β -phenylalanine	13.61	—	4.60	4.05
14. Proline	—	0.66	3.70	0.67
15. Tyrosine	—	17.72	2.31	1.46
16. Tryptophan	10.20	—	—	4.73
17. Threonine	—	—	4.60	—
18. Valine	8.51	—	—	6.62

(—) indicates absence.

The results show that all the seed proteins contain most of the essential amino acids. It has also

been shown that *H. integrifolia* seed protein is abundant with methionine (33.02%); *O. indicum* seed protein is rich in leucine (30.60%) and *V. calyculata* seed protein contains a high concentration of glycine (30.94%).

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